

Posters.science - User Experience

James ONeill¹, Nahid Zeinali¹, Sanjay Soundarajan¹, Bhavesh Patel^{1,*}

FAIR Data Innovations Hub, California Medical Innovations Institute, San Diego, CA, USA

*Contact: bpatel@calmi2.org

A. Overview

This document provides an overview of the user workflows for sharing and discovering scientific posters through Posters.science. This document will be used by our team to document our vision of Posters.science and develop the platform accordingly. It will also be used to get feedback from collaborators and potential users. It could ultimately serve as a basis for the user documentation of the Posters.science platform.

This document is structured as follows:

- In section B, we provide some background about Posters.science
- In section C, we provide an overview of the home page of Posters.science
- In section D, we describe the user interfaces for sharing posters
- In section E, we describe the user interfaces for finding posters

Throughout the write-up, "user" is used to refer to a fictitious user of the Posters.science platform, and the gender-neutral pronouns "they/their" are used to designate them.

B. Background

Millions of scientific posters are presented at conferences worldwide each year. Despite their value in showcasing early-stage research, novel findings, and emerging trends, most scientific posters disappear after the conference. While exact sharing rates are unknown, major repositories like Zenodo, Figshare, and F1000Research jointly host less than 52,000 posters from the last decade; a small fraction given that tens of millions must have been presented during this time. Studies estimate that less than 20% of posters are eventually published as papers, with some estimates as low as 2-3%. The average time from poster presentation to paper publication is approximately two years.

Even when posters are shared, they often lack standard metadata, making them difficult to find, reuse, and cite. This represents a significant missed opportunity for researchers, especially early-career scientists, to gain recognition, foster collaborations, and contribute to the broader scientific knowledge base.

To address these challenges, we are developing Posters.science, a free and open-source platform designed to increase the sharing and discovery of scientific posters. The platform will

be designed to make posters FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and AI-ready, maximizing their reach and impact.

With Posters.science, researchers will be able to upload their posters, and AI-powered tools will automatically extract rich metadata and generate a machine-friendly version (*poster.json* file). Posters will then be archived on trusted repositories (e.g, Zenodo) with a DOI assignment. The platform will also provide smart search capabilities, allowing users to ask complex research questions and instantly find relevant posters across the database.

During the first phase of development, Posters.science will index all posters from major open-access repositories (e.g., Zenodo and Figshare). The long-term goal is to create the largest registry of openly available scientific posters, turning millions of posters into a searchable, machine-friendly knowledge base that accelerates scientific discovery.

C. Homepage

The homepage of Posters.science will introduce the platform as a free, open-source solution for making scientific posters FAIR and AI-ready. A Hero section at the top will feature:

- A brief description of the platform and its mission
- Prominent "Share Poster" and "Find Posters" buttons for immediate action
- A tagline emphasizing ease of use and impact maximization
- Below the Hero section, multiple informational sections will provide context:
- Key Features: Highlights AI-powered metadata extraction, smart search capabilities, repository integration (e.g., Zenodo, Figshare), and FAIR compliance.
- Snapshot of the Project: Displays statistics such as posters indexed (e.g., 50,000+), disciplines covered (e.g., 25+ research fields), AI-powered enrichments (100% of posters), institutions involved (150+ universities), conferences represented (500+ academic conferences), and citations supported (10,000+ posters with DOIs).
- Sharing Posters: Brief overview of the four-step process; login, upload poster, review extracted metadata, and share to repository or download.
- Finding Posters: Overview of search capabilities, including standard search, Smart Search for natural language queries, and the Overview page with analytics.
- Community Engagement: Links to GitHub repository, documentation, and opportunities to contribute or provide feedback.

A navigation bar at the top will include the following sections: "Share Poster", "Find Posters", "About", "Documentation", and "Contact".

D. Sharing Posters

Clicking "Share Poster" will initiate a multistep workflow designed for simplicity and efficiency:

1. Login

Users will log in using email/password. Authentication will be required to enforce rate limits on AI/LLM-based tools and to allow users to track and update their previously shared posters.

2. Upload Poster File

Users will upload their poster PDF through a drag-and-drop interface or file browser. A minimum resolution of 300 DPI will be required to ensure readability. The platform will include automatic DPI validation for uploaded PDFs. In future phases, we will extend support to PowerPoint (PPT) and Word (DOCX) files.

Abstract submission will be optional and not required; most poster PDFs already contain their abstract. Users may optionally upload a standalone abstract PDF if they prefer to keep it separate. During the first phase of development, only the PDF format will be supported.

3. Review and Edit Metadata

The platform will automatically extract metadata from the poster PDF using Large Language Models (e.g., Llama 3.3 70B or similar depending on scaling and performance). While extraction is in progress, users will see a status indicator. Once complete, an editable form will display conveniently organized metadata across multiple sections. Metadata that will be automatically extracted is prefilled with confidence indicators that will allow users to focus on fields that may need review.

The metadata form will follow the machine-actionable poster JSON schema we are developing as part of this project, based on DataCite with poster-specific extensions. Mandatory fields (marked with *) include:

- Basic Information: Identifiers, creators/authors, institutional affiliations, titles, publisher name, and publication year
- Content Description: Abstract, keywords and subject terms, primary language (ISO 639-1 code)
- Dates and Events: Important dates (presented date, shared date), conference details (name, year)
- Poster Details: Resource type classification, file format (e.g., PDF), license information (e.g., CC-BY-4.0)

Optional fields will provide richer descriptions when available: related identifiers (links to papers or datasets), poster dimensions (e.g., "36x48 inches portrait") or file size, version information, ethics approvals (IRB protocols), figure and table captions, and research domain (e.g., "Clinical Medicine", "Machine Learning").

These mandatory metadata elements are deemed essential making posters FAIR based on internal discussions and consultation with collaborators including the University of California Curation Center (UC3).

4. Share or Download

Users will be able to share their poster package directly to a repository or download it locally. The poster package will include the PDF file of the poster and a *poster.json* file containing machine-readable metadata and extracted content following the machine-actionable poster JSON schema.

During the first phase, direct sharing to a repository (e.g., Zenodo) will be supported, with additional repositories (e.g., Figshare) planned for future phases. If shared to a repository (e.g., Zenodo) users will authenticate their account and will be presented with a deposition page showing files to be uploaded and metadata to be submitted (prefilled from Step 3). Upon clicking "Publish", the platform will create the Zenodo deposition, assign a DOI, and register the poster in the Posters.science database. Upon completion, users will receive links to both the Zenodo deposition and the poster's landing page on Posters.science.

If downloaded locally, the poster package will be saved as a zip file and the poster is registered in the Posters.science database. Users will be instructed to update their poster record with the DOI once available to ensure optimal findability.

E. Finding Posters

The discovery interface will provide multiple ways to search and explore posters:

E.1. Standard Search and Filtering

The discovery page will feature a search bar powered by a fast and scalable search engine (e.g., Meilisearch) optimized for relevance. The search engine should provide typo tolerance, instant search with real-time results, and sophisticated relevance ranking based on term frequency, document length, and field importance.

Users will be able to filter results by publication date range, conference, affiliation, and other criteria using a filtering menu. The platform may also incorporate custom semantic clustering and synonym collapsing to enhance search accuracy for domain-specific scientific terminology.

Search results will display each poster's title, authors, publication year, access type (open/controlled/closed), conference name, and primary subjects. Users will be able to download the record of returned posters as a JSON file for further analysis.

E.2. Poster Landing Pages

Clicking on any poster will lead to its dedicated landing page. Each landing page will display comprehensive metadata organized into sections:

- Core Information: Title, authors/creators with ORCIDs, affiliations with ROR IDs, publication year, and key dates, primary language
- Conference Details: Conference name, location, dates, acronym, website

- Content Description: Abstract, keywords, and subjects, domain/field of study
- Access and Rights: License information, access type, repository link, identifiers (DOI, Posters.science ID)
- Additional Details: Funding information with funder names and award numbers, poster dimensions and file format, related resources (papers, datasets), ethics approvals if applicable, version information

The landing page will also provide options to download the *poster.json* file for computational reuse and display extracted poster content sections when available.

E.3. Smart Search

Smart Search will allow users to ask natural language questions such as "What discoveries about Alzheimer's were presented at ARVO 2025?" The system will use semantic search powered by vector embeddings (e.g., 1024-dimensional vectors generated by the bge-large-en-v1.5 model) to find conceptually similar posters, not just keyword matches.

The process will involve embedding the user's query, performing vector similarity search against pre-computed poster embeddings stored in the database, retrieving the top 5 most relevant posters, and passing their content as context to a Large Language Model (e.g., Llama 3.3 70B). The LLM will generate a summary answer synthesizing information from the retrieved posters, with citations and links.

Results will include both the AI-generated summary and direct links to the 5 most relevant posters with their titles, authors, and relevance scores. Users will be able to download the record of returned posters as JSON for further analysis.

E.4. Overview Page

The Overview page will provide visualizations and analytics offering high-level insights into the Posters.science database:

- Poster Growth Over Time: Time-series chart showing monthly poster registration counts and conference diversity
- Top Institutions: Bar chart of the 20 institutions with the most posters, color-coded by region
- Research Domain Distribution: Hierarchical chart (e.g., treemap or sunburst chart) showing poster distribution across research fields
- Conference Landscape: Visualization (e.g., network graph or bubble chart) mapping the conference ecosystem
- Funding Landscape: Flow diagram (e.g., Sankey diagram) showing flows from funding organizations to research domains
- Geographic Distribution: World map displaying poster contributions by country (e.g., with choropleth coloring)
- Collaboration Networks: Graph visualization (e.g., force-directed graph) showing inter-institutional collaborations

All visualizations will be interactive, allowing users to filter, drill down into details, and export data. The dashboard will include a header with key summary metrics (total posters, institutions, conferences, countries) and supports time range filtering across all charts.